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Enigma of *Kutob*: An Exploration of the Guiding Voice of Filipinos

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Abstract

“Kutob” is a complex sensation that is rooted in Filipino culture that goes beyond the perspective of intuition. “Kutob” is essentially described as an intense feeling or awareness of one’s inner knowledge that goes beyond just a hunch and involves a person’s inner self, emotions, and intuition that defies logical reasoning. This paper utilizes information from a variety of sources, primarily online articles, and studies, to describe and explore the relationship of “Kutob” in Filipino culture. This study was able to expound the four components that can help understand “Kutob”, which are psychological, biological, social or the biopsychosocial model, and cultural factors. This study also related how “Kutob” is applied in the levels of Filipino core value: Kapwa. Highlighting the influence of “Kutob” influence on Filipino decision-making and where it was rooted are some of the main ideas of the study. This research findings suggests that a person’s “Kutob” does not generally comes from nothing or tacit, but rather is rotted from our own experiences from the past, biological influences, social understanding, one’s culture, and unconscious mind that this paper also elaborated. Moreover, this paper also has possible recommendations for future researchers and to Filipinos.

Keywords: *intuition, Filipino culture, inner knowing, psychological, biological, cultural, social, decision making*

Introduction

Filipino culture is an exuberant story that tells of the nation’s journey through the centuries (Jeanethpanti, 2022). The traditions and beliefs of Filipinos are both part of the history, this day and age, and what lies ahead (Bria, 2023) and serves as the living proof of how rich the Philippines are in terms of their cultural heritage, and these all reflect in the Filipino values, beliefs, and practices. According to Teresa Alcantara (2023), “Kutob” is a Filipino term that refers to an intuition or feeling of premonition and commonly associated with the term “foreboding” which is a sense or feeling that something bad is going to happen in the future in which “Kutob” does not “command” people what to do, but rather “suggests” what to do. While intuition occurs in day-to-day life, especially most apparent to professionals, there are times that regardless of years of experience, unconscious frameworks are used to make fast, high-quality decisions (Nalliah, 2016).

The concept of “Kutob” is complex and diverse. As per Thomas R. Very M.D. (2023), “Intuition is at the core of an epiphany; it is our own recognition and awareness of an idea or thought or vision for something that has yet to be discovered in the world—it is a complex interplay of our subconscious mind, our experiences, and our innate ability to sense patterns and connections that are not immediately obvious”. Mia Zhang (2024) stated that “Intuition is a powerful trait, yet often overlooked” all in which concludes the complexity of this grounded theory. As stated in the research of Clariza (2019, p. 1) The concept of “Kutob” in Filipino contexts can be explained by multiple factors that influence Filipino values. “Kutob” shapes how Filipino make decisions and unconsciously use it on a daily basis rooted in indigenous beliefs.

Clariza (2019) also supported that the Philippines is predominated by Catholicism; however, Filipinos believe in the existence of creative energy in the form of spirits that dwell in nature. These claims are all evident in Filipino ancestors because they depend on their knowledge and ability to rely on “Kutob” and thereby understand and adapt the cycle of their nature. This is all because The Philippines is located in the “Pacific Ring of Fire” known for frequent earthquakes and recurrent volcanic eruptions, the reason why Filipinos depend on ancestral knowledge and the ability to rely on intuition to fully grasp and comprehend the effects and impacts of nature’s cycles in order to survive,

Today, “Kutob” or intuition is beginning to be seen as part of the decision-making process approach (Glass, 2008) Although intuition is not fully recognized academically, it is becoming considered as an adequate and common way of deciding things because it gives people the power to look into the future in which they can prepare themselves for adversities as intuition allows for quality decisions to be made quickly, to manage the trade-off between speed and decision quality (Dane & Pratt, 2007).

As “Kutob” does not have an explanatory meaning in dictionary but rather given its foreign synonyms: hunch, intuition and gut feeling; the main objective of this research is to give “Kutob” a structured definition based on different concepts manifested in the Philippines to better explain behavior and as well as relating this phenomenon to foreign models to conclude a common ground, this paper will also help contribute to the foundation of Filipino Psychology. The researchers aim to reveal unexplored layers of this concept by exploring its roots and manifestations, as well as its relevance to the modern Filipino context. We also seek to deepen the scope of Filipino knowledge of indigeneity and demonstrate the importance of recognizing and preserving this concept in Filipino culture as “Kutob” is becoming a living testament to the continuity of cultural heritage to be able to help future research regarding this context.

Methodology

As this paper has a qualitative research design, the researchers then gathered multiple literature studies that will have a systematic literary review which will highlight common themes about the concept of “Kutob” from the combination of past and current journals and articles online, including those from National Library of Medicine, Science Direct, Psychology Today, and other sources. The researchers then looked into other topics related to the concept and gathered all of those ideas and information in order to produce a conclusion that helps them reach the purpose of the study and the objective of the group.

As Filipino Psychology was established in 1970s by Virgilio Enriquez; and is still a growing and establishing concept up to this day, the researchers considered and utilized all the materials available; even if it is more than 10 years ago to better explain and back up the phenomenon that has been manifesting in the Philippine context.

Results and Discussion

Conceptual Framework

The researchers have identified themes that have the most bearing on achieving the objectives of this paper after compiling existing relevant literature. These themes are “‘Kutob” in Different Aspects of English Language and Culture’, ‘Foreign Models Associated with Kutob’, ‘Biopsychosocial Model of “Kutob”, ‘Connection of Kutob in Existing Local Studies’, ‘Rational and Non-Rational Side of “Kutob”, and ‘Manifestation of “Kutob” in Pop Culture’.

The researchers used the following framework as a guide for the concept and structure of the paper in order to accomplish the study’s objectives:

When the self is confronted with a dilemma or an uncertain situation, “Kutob” tends to arise. In turn, this “Kutob”, can be influenced by one of the three groups to define its nature.

The first group, Past Experiences and Biological Influences, is usually rational in nature. The second group, Social by itself, is the kind of “Kutob” that can be rational or non-rational in nature. The last group, Unconscious Mind and Culture, is typically non-rational in nature. And once its nature is defined, “Kutob” will then manifest in the behavior of the individual through their decision or action.

Kutob in Different Aspects of English Language and Culture

“Kutob” has a lot of English translations and meanings but falls into the same context when translated into Filipino. According to Fatcher (2022), one of “Kutob” English translations is gut; gut feeling comes from patterns our body is familiar with or things that have happened already in our past. Gut feelings take place when your brain makes a substantial match or mismatch between what you have encountered in the past and what you are currently experiencing. Gut feeling and intuition have only slight differences in meaning. In intuitive thinking, the brain will try to process, recognize, and use the patterns that have already occurred in us. Past experiences are also helpful in intuitive thinking for the brain to have the best guess. However, both gut feeling and instinct is an act of trusting oneself;

trusting your gut and intuition is also an act of listening to your inner voice. These two things are both personal and a phenomenon that is hard to explain to others. Research states that people who have enough experience in a particular field may have more reliable mind intuition and gut feeling. The brain depends on the past experiences of a person and uses these experiences or occurrences to produce thoughts and predict the possibilities that could happen next. In relation to gut feeling and intuition, hunch could also be the English translation of “Kutob”. Oxford University Press (2024) defined hunch as guessing based on intuition more than deciding based on facts.

On the other hand, another translation of “Kutob” in the English language is instinct. According to Beer (2017), instinct is an inborn impulse or motivation to action typically performed in response to specific external stimuli. Instinct could be one factor why people act or decide in that way. Furthermore, there is another English translation of “Kutob” which is premonition. Unlike the other translations, premonition falls on the negative translation of “Kutob” in an English context. Premonition is a feeling that something is going to happen, especially in a pessimistic way (Oxford University Press, 2024).

Foreign Models Associated with Kutob

Sigmund Freud’s level of mind (Unconscious Level)

“Kutob” as translated to intuition or premonition that can be associated with Freud's concept of the unconscious mind. Freud believes that the mind is divided into three parts which are the conscious, preconscious, and the unconscious. According to him, the unconscious mind contains thoughts, desires, and memories that are not easily accessible to the conscious but still influences behavior and experience.

Similarly, “Kutob” represents a kind of knowing or feeling that is based or under the unconscious level and is deeply felt or sensed and is often described as the gut feeling or intuition. This level of Freud's idea of mind that operates the unconscious level plays a significant role in shaping thought, feelings, and behaviors of individuals.

Carl Jung’s Archetypes and Collective Unconscious

A concept of Jung that correlates to the notion of “Kutob” is the collective unconscious. It is defined as the experiences of our ancestors that have been passed down to different generations (Allen, 2020). Despite the fact that these beliefs are not genuinely inherited, the way Filipinos respond to and resolve particular issues speaks for itself. In particular, most Filipino folklore and mythology feature Bathala and our ancestor’s pamahiin. This shows their adherence to religion and superstition which greatly affects how “Kutob” manifests in their behavior or decisions. According to Jung, an individual may have as many of these inherited tendencies because of various and countless experiences they may have. Repetition of these inherited tendencies created the Archetypes.

Jung introduced Archetypes as ancient or archaic images that derive from the collective unconscious. He also stated that this should be distinguished from instincts (Feist et al., 2018, p. 112) In relation to “Kutob”, Archetypes and Instincts are unconsciously determined, and both similarly affect behavior or personality. Known as ‘Wise old man’, this archetype is symbolic imagery of a person with profound wisdom and intuitive knowledge. This archetype typically acts as a mentor who guides a person beyond their typical awareness. This relates to the Filipino concept of “Kutob”, which denotes gut feeling or premonition. When a person experiences “Kutob”, they seem to have a great sense of intuition which connects them to their inner wisdom.

Albert Bandura’s Social learning theory

There’s also another theory that talks about learning through observing and imitating the observable behavior of others. According to Albert Bandura’s Social learning theory, both cognitive and environmental factors interact to affect observable behavior and the learning process.

This study tells how observing others can influence one’s thinking. In relation to “Kutob”, these observed behavior and actions from other people can be used by our minds as a basis to where that “Kutob” feeling came from. With “Kutob” being an observed behavior, it reinforces both rational and irrational aspects that succeed the “Kutob” felt by the individual.

Biopsychosocial Model of Kutob

“Kutob” manifests itself in different aspects, may it be biological, psychological, or social which showcases the influence and guidance it gives to an individual. To further understand the interaction and relationship of “Kutob” to these factors, the biopsychosocial model is supplied to provide in-depth assessment. The model also serves as an explanation on why and how such phenomena takes place in everyday lives, and decision making of Filipinos.

Biological Aspect of Kutob in Existing Studies and Research

As we hear the old saying and common advice of our peers “trust your gut” or in Filipino language, “depende kung ano nakukutuban mo...” Russel Fatcher referred to this expression as trusting your feelings or intuition. He explained that this phrase means to trust your inner voice, a hunch that something is about to happen, or your decision is good or bad. The brain is said to be delicately linked to the other organs of our body and some neuroscientists believe that the mind is a knitted network of the brain and body. Gut feelings require biological or physical manifestations such as unusual feelings in the stomach, getting goosebumps, and/or sometimes dryness of your

throat or sore throat.

According to Peter Holzer's study in 2022 under the National Library of Medicine, signals from the gut arriving at the brain influence affect, emotion, and cognition including beliefs and decision-making. He stated that experts show evidence that gastrointestinal function can be greatly affected by stress and emotion. Sigmoidoscopy, a procedure used to screen for colon and rectal cancers, was performed by Almy and Tulin (1947) to volunteer medical students. During the procedure, a hoax was mentioned to the students regarding their findings. This resulted in observations of strong muscle contractions and an increase in blood flow in the rectum. After they explained the hoax, the alterations of the organ and blood abruptly subsided. Mayer and Taché's studies prove that acute physical and emotional stress can indeed affect one's digestive tract. The main symptom that can be observed is slowing down the coordinated movement of the bowels and its secretion or "being heavy on the stomach".

Psychological Aspect of Kutob Based on Fears and Experiences

"Kutob" These can be driven by our feelings of uncertainty and possible fears that can cause anxiety which can protect us from harmful situations. The past occurrences in our lives may be a lesson or a constant reminder for us that influence our consciousness and may turn into fear, sometimes, it can be an underlying factor in "Kutob". The human system is precautioned by these fears, thus facing unfamiliar situations might be associated with these past experiences. (Mbanali, 2019) With the guide of these subconsciousness instincts, it can usefully help and guide us better in making calculated decisions.

Social Aspect of Kutob: in Kapwa

Connecting "Kutob" in the Filipino context, we could integrate it with the topics of pakiramdam, and kagandahang loob. To start, "Kutob" is a form of knowledge that is a result of cumulative experience that requires a person to perceive the situation they are in and be sensitive to cues. Similarly, this nature of "Kutob" is what makes it difficult to describe as it is not a tangible concept that develops, manifests, and results in different ways depending on what triggered the feeling: a person, place, or event. It could manifest as a hesitation that prevents brash actions that could affect others when not observed in an insightful manner. While viewing "Kutob" in the context of "kagandahang loob", one could feel this tacit knowledge as a sign of one's shared social value. Some manifestations of kapwa differ depending on where the opposing person falls on the relationship category of an individual. Similar to proximity principle in social psychology, physical distances could influence the way "Kutob" manifests. For example, a person viewed as within the "one-of-us" category, typically achieved when both parties have developed initial rapport, may manifest "Kutob" in a manner that will drastically affect their decision-making as this is rooted, not only to a mutual understanding of a person's shared identity but also through a shared value of humanity respected towards both parties. While physical distance towards that individual could make "Kutob" manifest in different ways depending on their proximity towards each other, with behaviors such as anxiousness and worry increasing with distance, and comfort and security increasing the lesser the distance to that person they are. Furthermore, manifestations of "Kutob" may also take the form of general unprovoked gestures of generosity towards strangers. Furthermore, when a person feels "Kutob" towards a person who they have not built sufficient rapport with, it could manifest as a measurement that could be used to gauge whether the person has ill intentions towards you or people you know. In a study conducted by Pagaduan-Lopez, Chua, and De Guzman (2012) towards victims of rape, several survivors have described an ill feeling or "sixth sense" that predates the attack. Similarly, physical distances influence "Kutob", with perceived intimidation increasing as the individual gets closer to the person, and perceived safety increasing the farther the individual is towards the person. Although this manifestation of "Kutob" may not encompass the essence of the word, the concept of subjective awareness could be a signifier that an individual is in near impending danger. This could also stem into an unconscious experience you fail to immediately recall with similar circumstances that may or may not have ended well in your favor. Thus, when "Kutob" is connected to kapwa, it could be understood as a collective characteristic that all Filipinos have, at the same time, not restricted towards individuals that are under a person's outsider category, referring towards individuals that a person has not built enough rapport with, nor it is exclusive towards people who are viewed as "one-of-us", referring to people viewed by an individual to have had closer relationships.

The concept of "Kutob" can be used as a tool to judge a person's character in the context of kapwa and other values. It could be utilized as a gauge of a person's character in a sense that you do not want the wrong people to have a negative impact towards your inner circles, at the same time, you could use "Kutob" as a means of feeling whether a person would make a decision you think would bear unfortunate consequences.

Rational and Non-Rational side of Kutob

One of the positive things that "Kutob" guided the indigenous Filipinos where they have used "Kutob" to estimate or help predict from the signs of possible natural phenomena that may occur given the fact that in geographical terms where the Philippines is placed within the Pacific Ring of Fire facing the Western Pacific Ocean that have been vital for Filipino survival. (Clariza, n.d.). According to Galacgac and Balisacan in 2009, Filipino farmers based on their environmental observations like in astronomic and atmospheric conditions, as well as to plants and the behavior of animals like birds, fishes, and livestock. Stormgeo (2019) discussed that the heightened senses of animals can immediately sense these changes in weather and often behave strangely. In addition to that, it has been stated that "Birds and bees also appear to be able to sense this drop in barometric pressure and will instinctively seek the cover of their nests or hives" that guides them to fly to safer places. In this sense Filipino farmers helps them with their "Kutob" in relevance to

pakiramdam as a guide to survive.

On the other hand, “Kutob” does not always have certainty. As stated, a gut feeling, or an instinct is having to know something which does not automatically mean it is based on facts; you just know it. Reckoning and relying on every decision you make on what you feel is right from your gut can be unreliable and unpredictable. These unforeseen results of a person based on his/her “Kutob” may lead to disappointment. Moreover, trusting and basing all your way from it because you think that it always works might be a case of purposely ignoring and not believing in facets that are legitimate and based on facts which can cause harm to you and the people around you.

Filipinos’ “Kutob” may be associated with the confrontative surface value which is *bahala na* or also known as tacit trust. The aforementioned “Kutob” as a guiding voice without certainty and assurance can be somehow connected to Lagmay’s definition of ‘bahala na’ He interpreted this concept to determination and risk-taking in the face of possible failure. This depicts the idea of Filipinos to trust their “Kutob” especially when placed in second thoughts or something negative is bound to happen.

Connection of Kutob in Existing Local Studies

“Kutob” in Filipino studies has yet to be studied in a deeper and more thorough manner, as there is not much to be found when searching for relevant literature. However, in the UP Diksyunaryong Filipino, they were able to construct several definitions for “Kutob”, being the following: (1) a feeling or a belief of what is about to happen or has just transpired; (2) that guilt pang when your conscience moves you; (3) the noise one makes when you move around a tight space; and (4) something that could be related to the beat of the heart or an upset stomach (Aguilera, 2017).

That being the case, Aguilera also mentioned that “Kutob” can be translated into several English words, but none of them can capture its true meaning. “Kutob” means 'intuition' or 'hunch', but “Kutob” is closer to something tangible, or even something real. “Kutob” as 'gut feeling', but it stems from a deeper aspect of our personality. “Kutob” can be either 'premonition' or 'ill-omen', but it can go both ways—not just bad or good. And just like with other Filipino words, a prefix or suffix can change the word entirely, with “Kutob” also being a verb, like 'kinukutuban ako; kinutuban ako'. With that, a person constantly feeling a “Kutob” can be considered gifted with psychic abilities or clairvoyance.

But in the Philippines, a place that believes in magic and the mythical, where our ancestors had a deep connection with nature, we speak in a language that is transcendental and beyond words. According to Guia-Samuels (2023), this language is the ability to discern the innermost intention of someone through intuition. To further explain, she associated it with 'Pakikiramdam', wherein you try to feel someone's 'Loob', the very essence of a person, whether it be their intention or motivation. And Filipino ancestral wisdom is based on perceiving someone's true nature and following what they feel, like how a person would let their feet wander and trust whatever their destination would be.

Kutob in Popular Media

“Kutob” a Filipino Film by Javier Reyes

“Kutob” also known as foreboding in English (is a feeling or sense that something bad is going to happen) it is a psychological movie that revolves around the story of a woman and a man who is in a relationship. The woman named Ericka suspected that her boyfriend (Carlo) is having an affair. A fortune teller read a tarot card for Ericka and said that something bad will happen and warns them that the danger is lurking around as someone watches her and has a hidden desire. Ericka ignores this and her relationship with her boyfriend gets worse and that is where the danger starts as Lemuel approaches and takes advantage of the situation.

This psychological film from 2005 was directed by Jose Javier Reyes. The movie revolves around a series of horrifying murders in the town with suspicion falling into various characters of Lemuel that was played by Marvin Augustin. The film explores the concept of paranoia, revenge, and the dark side of human nature.

If it is applied in Filipino belief, “Kutob” is always associated with a gut feeling or intuition about something, especially something bad or negative. It is seen as a kind of feeling or warning that people should pay attention to. In the part of the movie where it was seen that Ericka has already had “Kutob” intuition about her boyfriend affair and the fortune teller’s warning can be an example of this belief. This demonstrates how “Kutob” can serve as a warning sign and how ignoring it can lead to negative consequences and the belief of listening and acknowledging these feelings can help people navigate potentially dangerous situations.

“Tarot” a Filipino Film by Juan R. Lana

Meanwhile, the movie Tarot (2009) has made the manifestation of “Kutob” as a centerfold and driving point of the plot. It centered around the protagonist Cara’s “Kutob” as she had constantly felt a constant feeling that was not explained blatantly in the film. Using the power of the tarot cards, she has constantly predicted multiple events that would constitute misfortune towards her and the people with her. One instance was presented early in the film when she predicted that there would be snowfall, which happened. Additionally, she also got upset when she predicted that two of her family members would die, which also happened. In connection with the information gathered above, “Kutob” is somewhat a premonition that can be good or bad. Clearly, Cara’s predictions were not in favor of her which resulted in her hurting and getting her upset.

Although the film has framed “Kutob” in its supernatural nature, there is a hypothesis that could be constructed here whether there is a hereditary component to Cara’s ability from her grandmother as she has inherited it from her grandmother. “Kutob” in the Philippine popular media show that this is commonly used in fortune telling or predictions, especially with our ancestors that tend to be passed down to generations. This may seem inexplicable, it somehow made sense to native and true Filipinos. Furthermore, “Kutob” used as a guide for Filipinos was evident in the film. It showed how Cara’s intuition, of course with the help of the tarot cards, affected her decisions with the conflict around her and her reactions facing the consequences. The presence of “Kutob” has been persistent and remained sophisticated through the entire movie, therefore it could be derived that there is a detailed explanation under its multiple manifestation in multiple Filipino contexts.

“Mallari” a Filipino Film by Roderick Cabrido

Mallari takes inspiration from the story of Fr. Juan Severino Mallari, a parish priest of Magalang, Pampanga who was executed for committing 57 murders in the 1800s, classifying him as the first and only recorded Filipino serial killer. In an attempt to stop this from happening, an adult Jonathan goes to Magalang after having premonitions concerning his fiancée, Agnes. Lucas, the son of a household worker, goes with him. Lucas’s niece Amal informs Jonathan about the history of his ancestors. After he arrives, a man posing as a priest targets juvenile offenders with a string of murders that cast suspicion on Jonathan. Jonathan admits to Lucas that he believes Severino might be involved, recalling his early nightmares and predicting that Lucas would attack Agnes shortly.

“The Killer Bride” a Filipino Series by Diosdado “Dado” C. Lumibao

“The Killer Bride” is a Filipino teleserye that perfectly integrates the idea of “kutob” into its story. It explores the complex web of connected lives that are haunted by hidden mysteries, unresolved traumas, and the constant searching for the truth. The lines between the supernatural and the actual world become more complicated as Camila’s “kutob” intensifies throughout the course of the show. She moves through a world in which the ghosts of the past spread big and significantly impact the present. Camila uses her intuition to guide her through a web of deceptions, secrets, and betrayals like a compass. Furthermore, Camila’s “kutob” is not just based on her personal experiences. She gains empathy for those around her and develops a keen sense of their reasons for doing things. In addition to Camila, several characters in “The Killer Bride” also experience with “kutob” in various forms. This includes Vito’s haunting memories, Emma’s cryptic visions, and Fabio’s frightening premonitions. Every character is impacted by the mysterious force of intuition, which shapes their futures in unexpected ways.

“Noli Me Tangere” and “El Filibusterismo” by Dr. Jose Rizal

Branching towards Philippine literature, the great novels of esteemed Jose Rizal, ‘Noli Me Tangere’ and ‘El Filibusterismo’ also display “Kutob” as a theme or element as the novel progresses and delves deeper into the lives of the characters. Set during the 19th century in the Philippines, the novels were filled with symbolism pertaining to the struggles of the Filipinos under the hands of the Spaniards. Here, intuition plays the role of a guide for the characters to navigate the oppressive colonial society, even without conscious reasoning. It helped them understand their social and political stand and lead them in situations that came along with it.

For instance, Maria Clara experienced several premonitions through vivid dreams, highlighting some sort of mystical link between her and the characters, mostly her partner and the protagonist, Crisostomo Ibarra. Continuing with this, Crisostomo Ibarra’s transformation into the known jeweler Simoun in the start of *El Filibusterismo*, wherein he used his intuition as a way of finding out the strengths and weaknesses of the characters he encountered, finding out whether they would be beneficial for his plans or would be his enemies, shows a different way on how to utilize “Kutob” and different ways it could manifest.

Overall, this phenomenon is a common theme in Filipino pop culture that resonates with many people, as it taps into the universal experience of relying on our intuition and gut feelings in several aspects of life. These references reflect the belief in pop culture about the power of intuition, this suggests that this phenomenon can serve as a tool in navigating life’s uncertainties, mysteries and a valid source of information that can guide individuals to make decisions that can potentially change individuals’ life.

Conclusion

The phenomenon of “Kutob” does not necessarily only exist in the Filipino culture and context. The definitions of “Kutob” are all synonymous and interrelated with foreign definitions of gut, hunch, instinct, premonition, and intuition. Although what makes “Kutob” distinct to the

Filipinos is its underlying factor that is embedded in our culture. Even then, it is evident that indigenous Filipinos have used and based their decisions in “Kutob” in relation to pakiramdam to help them save their way of living and to survive.

In the present day, “Kutob” plays a significant role in Filipinos’ decision making, it is recommended to understand the strengths of it as we are sometimes taught to devalue it due to having no basis and just a “feeling” and is not reliable. On the other hand, “Kutob” can be detrimental when it hinders us from believing what is proved to be right and legitimate. With that, it is important to balance “Kutob” with other existing factors, it can work hand in hand with foreseeable signs and facts which will produce helpful results in making decisions.

The researchers therefore conclude that us Filipinos continuously use “Kutob” not entirely based on a guess or feeling, but alongside observations and past experiences, memories, biological influences, social understanding, one’s culture, and unconscious mind that guide us to know what is unknown.

Thus, the researcher recommends a further study of “Kutob”, focusing more on its implications and significance, basing it both on Filipino and Western Culture. This study also suggests possible implications to other cultures that manifest the enigma of “Kutob” as an exploration of the guiding voice of an individual.

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